

Optimization of Photo-enhanced Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄ Nanocomposite to Degrade Chlorpyrifos Commercial Pesticide

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Abstract

Excess uses of pesticides lead to contamination of water bodies posing risks to both the environment as well as human health. In this work, authors focused on photocatalytic degradation of Chlorpyrifos (liquid 20%) commercial grade pesticide degraded by using Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄ synthesized nanocomposite under natural irradiation and found significant progress about 74.98 % degradation of pesticide. The efficacy of the synthesized nanocomposite for pesticide removal was indicated. The simple co-precipitation method was followed to obtain a nanocomposite of Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄ and characterized by SEM, XRD, BET, UV-visible, and FTIR to analyze the nature of the phase. The efficiency of the photocatalytic degradation process was optimized by various factors, such as the pesticide concentration, irradiation reaction time, and catalyst dosage. An increasing pesticide concentration resulted in a slower degradation rate and suggested increased catalyst dosage to enhance the removal efficiency. Additionally, longer reaction times exhibited improved degradation rates, demonstrating the time-dependent nature of the photocatalytic process. The results highlighted the potential of the Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄ nanocomposite as a promising photocatalyst for pesticide degradation, emphasizing the need for further investigation into its mechanism and optimization of reaction parameters for enhanced efficiency with altered future modification.

Keywords: Chlorpyrifos; Environment; Hazardous Pesticide; Irradiation; Nanocomposite.

1. Introduction

The growth of the global industrial sector has sparked worries about pollution, water scarcity, and climate change. The growth of specialized and technologically advanced industries has expanded the diversity of pollutants entering the environment in addition to the number of pollutants.

Figure 1: Types of Pesticides

The widespread use of pesticides prompts concerns about their potential to pollute water and impact human health. Pesticides are substances used to eradicate and manage weeds and pests. These substances are frequently used in agriculture to control diseases and pests away from crops. According to their origin and kind of pest, pesticides are categorized, as Figure 1 illustrates[1–4].

Pesticide residues are found in streams and shallow water across the world, with amounts varying by location and season. Most pesticides' active concentrations are resistant to degradation in the environment. Their highest and lowest levels exist throughout the summer and winter seasons, respectively. Pesticides enter aquatic habitats by leaching, surface runoff, spray drift, soil erosion, and volatilization. There are two parts to pesticides: the active and the inert. The chemical compounds in pesticides function to eliminate, manage, or repel pests. The term "inert component" refers to the component that remains. The rapid increase in the use of herbicides increased agricultural productivity and intensification. Since pesticides contaminate groundwater and surface water, they have a negative impact on human health and are a serious problem in many nations. Water recycling is significantly hindered by the presence of toxic organic compounds in wastewater discharge. The laws and regulations of each state can be followed while using pesticides. Pesticide residue in the environment, especially in water, may have negative consequences. While there are several remediation options available for soil and water polluted by pesticides, choosing the most appropriate one is still difficult. To eliminate persistent pollutants, several methods have been proposed and are now being implemented. Air stripping, membrane filtration, biological degradation, and surface adsorption are examples of conventional methods for eliminating contaminants. Although effective, the above-mentioned strategies have limitations in terms of cost, time, applicability, and efficacy. Several technologies, including photolysis, photo-Fenton, semiconductor-based photocatalysis, and photo electrocatalysis, are employed to manage pesticide concentrations in the natural environment. Among these, photocatalysis based on semiconductors has sparked a lot of attention since it is more practical and degrades faster, which encourages mineralization [9]. Because of their small size and special qualities, semiconducting nanomaterials are of interest for the remediation of many different types of environmental contaminants, including organic pesticides[5–9].

The preparation of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-CO}_3\text{O}_4$ nanocomposite for pesticide degradation, adsorption, and other contamination removal from water has been extensively studied by scientists. Of those materials, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-CO}_3\text{O}_4$ has drawn the most attention due to its superior electrochemical stability and electrocatalytic activity as well as its low cost for extensive applications. As a result, fixing metal oxides in graphene oxide will boost the efficiency in various pesticide degradation applications.

Photocatalysis is a basic process in which a photon of light with energy equal to or above the bandgap energy creates a charge-carrier pair. The energy change causes the generation of electrons and holes, resulting in the production of hydroxide and other radicals that help degrade organic pollutants. The catalyst's photocatalytic activity is based on its capacity to form electron-hole pairs, which then produce

free radicals. Photocatalysis effectively degrades and mineralizes most organic and inorganic contaminants, making it a significant benefit[10–15].

Figure 2. Worldwide percentage consumption of pesticides (FAOSTAT,2024).

In the past few years, physicochemical (advanced oxidation process) and conventional biological treatment approaches have been widely employed for pesticide removal. However, the byproducts of this process are more toxic than the parent compound along with an incomplete degradation of pesticide. Even though many researchers synthesized Co_3O_4 , relatively no study has been found to fulfill, this requirement. The $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ catalyst prepared by the co-precipitation heating method showed significant results (Borsule *et al.*,2020). Nanocomposite was characterized by various techniques and was then examined for their environmental and energy applications. Co_3O_4 is an excellent p-type semiconductor with effective properties having high absorption in the solar spectrum. Co_3O_4 is a technologically important material with a wide range of applications in lithium-ion batteries, heterogeneous catalysis, gas sensing, ceramic pigments, electrochemical devices, and high-temperature solar selective absorbers.

Authors were discussed the preparation of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ materials to investigate their possible use in the degradation of pesticides. Here, we focus on characterizing $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ composites. This article covers the methods for removing pesticides from aqueous media that use semiconductor-based photocatalytic processes and discusses how the materials have been modified, how they underwent testing, and the extent to which the materials degraded overall. The article concludes that one potential method for getting rid of pesticides from aqueous systems is photocatalytic degradation. In the future, semiconductor-based photocatalytic technology needs to perform better and scale up for actual environmental conditions.

2. Materials And Methods

Chlorpyrifos EC (CAS No. 2921-88-2), 20%purity, (IUPAC Name: O,O-Diethyl O-(3,5,6-trichloropyridin-2-yl) phosphorothioate) was obtained from Fertilizer shop, Belagavi, India. Al_2O_3 , MgO , Co_3O_4 composite was prepared by simple wet-chemical method using 1g each of $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1:1:1 ratio) by adding 100 mL ethanol to each beaker separately

dropwise and stirred for 30 min. by maintaining the pH at the range 7-8 by using 1N of each NaOH and H₂SO₄. Both the precursor of MgO doped with Al₂O₃ and then co-doped with Co₃O₄ by adding a drop wise keeping continuous stirring for 3 hours. Then added 1 N NaOH dropwise until the solution gets precipitated. Then centrifuged the synthesized material by removing the supernatant liquid and washed it several times with double distilled water. Then material was dried in an oven for 1 hour to remove moisture. Then, calcinated the material at 270 °C for 3 hours. Finally, a synthesized composite material (Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄) was stored air tight container. All other chemicals used for the experiments were of analytical grade reagents and obtained from s d fine chem-limited, Mumbai, India.

3. Materials Characterization

The synthesized Al₂O₃-MgO incorporated Co₃O₄ nanocomposite were characterized by nature of phases through (XRD) X-ray diffractometer (BRUKER:D8 advance related Cu-K α radiation $\lambda=0.154$ nm in the range of 2θ values 10-80 Å Carl Zeiss AG-ULTRA55 Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM) with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy of the samples (200KV) A Perkin Elmer spectra RX-1 model spectrophotometer was used to record the IR spectra of KBr pellets. The optical absorbance and photo response of Al₂O₃-MgO co-doped Co₃O₄ nanocomposites were determined using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer, model USB 4000, made by Ocean Optics, U.S.A. The specific surface area was determined using the Brunner-Emmett-Teller (BET) technique, whereas the desorption using the Baret-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method.

4. Pesticide Solution Preparations

Before the experiment 0.25 mL pesticide (commercial grade) was added to the 500 mL DW to prepare 10 ppm and stirred for 10 min. to mix well.

5. Result And Discussion

5.1 Structural analysis

The structural and morphological change has been reflected by the variations in XRD patterns of synthesized nanocomposite (Fig. 3) these diffraction peaks in XRD correspond to JCPDS card No.80-0075. The 2θ values are found with (311), (400), and (511) for Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄, respectively.

Figure 3. X-Ray diffraction pattern of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ nanocomposite.**Figure 4.** UV-visible spectra of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ nanocomposite.

5.2 Optical properties

The UV-Spectrophotometer, (Fig. 4) which records in the 300-700 nm range, is the best and exclusively used instrument for determining the optical characteristics of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ nanocomposite. The sample is prepared at room temperature, here the energy gap associated with characteristics was evaluated using the UV-visible diffuse reflectance spectrum. UV-visible used to examine the impact of the metal oxides on other metal oxides and composite.

5.3 FE-SEM Scanning Electron Microscopy

FE-SEM for in-detail inspection of the nano-composite, we performed scanning electron microscopy which is essential characterization to know the morphological structure of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ nanocomposite to study the composition and surface of the nanocomposite. The nanocomposite shows a spherical shape (Fig. 5) with a wide surface area, which correspondence to BET analysis. The surface area often results in better reaction sites and better adsorption capacity of the photocatalyst. $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-Co}_3\text{O}_4$.

Figure 5. Surface morphological of Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄ nanocomposite (FE-SEM)

The N₂ adsorption/desorption tests at 77K were used to investigate the BET-specific surface of Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄ interpreted in the graph (Fig. No. 4. a and b). The specific surface area is 14.065(m²/g)and the pore diameter is 0.051178 (cm²/g) (Table 1.) This was considered a good specific surface area for the photocatalytic activity.

Figure 6. Nitrogen adsorption –desorption isotherm of Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄ nanocomposite.**Table 1.** The volume pore size and specific surface area of the composite.

Samples	Pore volume (cm ² /gm)	Pore size (nm)	Surface area (m ² /g)
Composite	0.051178	14.555	14.065

5.5 FTIR Spectra of prepared samples

The results of the FTIR spectroscopy of Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄ are depicted in (Fig7). The pattern O-H group stretches towards the vibration band 1500 cm⁻¹. The carbonyl functional groups of composite C=O peaks are observed at 600 cm⁻¹. The metal-oxide bands appeared in the fingerprint region 400-700 cm⁻¹.

Figure 7. Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄

6. Photocatalytic Experiments

The photocatalytic activity of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ nanocomposite was investigated using UV-visible absorption spectra obtained during the breakdown of chlorpyrifos in an aqueous solution at ambient temperature. A stirred combination of catalyst and Chlorpyrifos solution was always exposed for one hour in the dark prior to exposure to create an equilibrium between the adsorption and desorption processes of the Chlorpyrifos molecule on the catalyst surface. Natural sunlight was used to expose the pesticide solution and photocatalyst to sunlight to assess their photocatalytic behavior. The Chlorpyrifos solution was collected at regular intervals during the radiation process. To assess the level of deterioration, a sample (5 ml) was taken at predetermined intervals and centrifuged for three minutes at 2500 rpm [16–19].

6.1 Assessment of photocatalytic activity

The catalytic behavior of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ nanocomposite was examined using photocatalytic degradation of chlorpyrifos under the same ideal circumstances as natural sunshine. $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ nanocomposite for photocatalytic characteristic absorption values have been used to monitor the pesticide at 298.7 nm, respectively. The percentage rate of pesticide breakdown at $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ nanocomposite as a function of irradiation duration is displayed in Figure 8.

6.2 Effect of initial Chlorpyrifos concentration

Figure 8. Effect of initial concentration (inset) on the photocatalytic degradation of pesticide with $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ catalyst dose of 5 mg at natural pH at different time interval.

The influence of Chlorpyrifos concentration on photocatalytic efficacy was examined using a variety of Chlorpyrifos concentrations (10, 20, 30, and 40 ppm) and a fixed amount (10 mg) of the optimal

photocatalyst, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-CO}_3\text{O}_4$. Figure 8 (inset) illustrates how the photocatalytic degradation fraction rises as pollutant concentrations rise. Additionally, when pesticide concentrations increase, the reaction mixture gets more turbid, which lowers the effectiveness of degradation by preventing light photons from reaching the catalyst's active sites. Consequently, a better efficacy in removing chlorpyrifos may be achieved with a lower dose of 30 ppm. The fact that additional Chlorpyrifos molecules were adsorbed on the photocatalyst's surface when the initial Chlorpyrifos concentration was raised may help to explain this. The results indicate that the Chlorpyrifos solution concentration of 30 ppm and the catalyst dosage of 10 mg for the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-CO}_3\text{O}_4$ nanocomposite at a natural pH were set for more investigation after 90 minutes of exposure to sunlight[16–25].

6.3 Effect of Catalyst dose

The effects of different catalyst concentrations ranging from 5 mg to 20 mg were examined to maximize the efficiency of Chlorpyrifos breakdown while maintaining a concentration of 30 ppm. (Figure.9) shows how well the catalyst degrades chlorpyrifos. The enhanced photocatalytic degradation was brought on by a greater catalyst amount (5 to 20 mg), indicating that the rate of degradation rises with increasing catalyst dosage. The surface catalyst's higher number of active sites might help to explain this. Therefore, the quantity of deterioration depends on the amount of catalyst. When the catalyst dosage is raised to 20 mg, the reaction mixture cannot homogenize efficiently at a certain agitation rate, which leads to lower catalytic activity (Figure 9). As a result, the active centers stop functioning. Because it prevents radiation from reaching the center of the solution, catalytic activity decreases as catalyst dosage increases. When the catalyst dosage exceeded 15 mg, the rate of Chlorpyrifos breakdown was slowed.

Figure 9. Effect of catalyst dose (inset) on the photocatalytic degradation of pesticide with $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-CO}_3\text{O}_4$ catalyst dose of 5 mg at natural pH at different time interval.

6.4 Effect of pH

The pH of the dye is one of the most crucial factors that might affect the dye breakdown process on the photocatalyst surface. The effects of varying pH values from 3 to 11 (acidic, neutral, and basic pH values) on the breakdown efficiency of chlorpyrifos were investigated by adding the proper quantity of 0.1M H₂SO₄ and NaOH. (Figure 10) summarizes the findings. Researchers used photocatalyst nanocrystals at different pH levels (3, 5, 7, 9, and 11) in the original Chlorpyrifos solution (30 ppm) and a fixed amount (15 mg) of the Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄ optimum photocatalyst to evaluate the Chlorpyrifos photocatalytic degradation to observe how pH impacts the activity. Utilizing a 15 mg dose of Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄ catalyst and a 30ppm initial concentration of the chlorpyrifos solution under 90 minutes of solar exposure. The breakdown efficiency of Chlorpyrifos was shown to be higher in a neutral pH than in other pH ranges.

Figure 10. Effect of pH on the photocatalytic degradation of pesticide (inset).

6.5 Stability

The recyclability of the finished nanocrystal was verified to evaluate the stability of the photocatalyst. The repeated photodegradation of chlorpyrifos over five cycles is seen in Figure 11. To prepare for the subsequent cycles, the Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄ nanocrystals were separated by centrifugation at the end of each cycle, washed in double-distilled water, and reconstituted with a fresh Chlorpyrifos solution. After 90 minutes of reaction time, the photocatalytic performances for the five-cycle reuses were 79.1, 75, 71, 66, and 57%, respectively and the degradation path has been proposed in Figure 10.

Figure 11. (a) Photocatalytic stability of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO-Co}_3\text{O}_4$ nanocomposites with pesticide under natural light irradiation.

Figure 12 (a) chemical structure of Chlorpyrifos pesticide (b) General proposed degradation pattern[26].

Conclusion

The samples' single-phase formation is confirmed by the powder XRD data analysis. Measurements of the photocatalyst's optical band gap reveal that they are semiconducting. At 200 °C, the Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄ FESEM-estimated average crystal size increases from around 50 to 65 nm. The Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄ band gap diminishes when the UV-visible absorption edge shifts towards longer wavelengths. The addition of chlorpyrifos in our study causes a maximum deterioration of 79.1%. The degradation of chlorpyrifos insecticide, which may be used as a photocatalyst to exploit sunlight, is significantly influenced by the average crystal size of the Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄ nanocomposite and its band gap. Notably, Al₂O₃-MgO-Co₃O₄ may be regenerated for better cyclic stability and functions effectively as a catalyst to degrade the pesticide chlorpyrifos in a neutral environment.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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